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پنجمین کنفرانس بین المللی

The Relationship Between Iranian EFL learners' Social Class, Their Willingness to Communicate and Tendency to Achieve Higher Degree of Proficiency

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between a group of Iranian EFL language learners' social class, willingness to communicate, and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. Fifty-five participants (N= 55) (26 males and 29 females) were selected randomly. Two different of questionnaires were distributed among participants simultaneously. A willingness to communicate and a social class questionnaire were used to determine the social class of the learners and a third questionnaire was administered to find out the participants' tendency to achieve higher proficiency levels. The obtained statistical analyses using ANOVA and Pearson Correlation indicated a significant relationship between the variables.

Keywords: Proficiency, social class, willingness to communicate

1. INTRODUCTION

English Language has become increasingly important in everyday life. It is used and practiced everywhere in the world and in the Middle East. In examining L2 language pedagogy of the present era, it is believed that communicative language teaching (CLT) is going ahead of other methods during the 21 century (Yu, 2009). As Savignon (2005) states, "the essence of communicative language teaching is the engagement of language learners in communication to allow them to develop their communication competence" (p. 16). It is, therefore, assumed that understanding and identification of learners' communication orientation and needs provide a basis for language teachers to design curricula, apply instructional strategies, and improve language teaching effectiveness (Hsu, 2005).

According to Yu (2009), theoretical examination and pedagogical application throughout the current decade have primarily promoted the important role of using language to communicate in L2 learning and teaching. Moreover, it is argued that the ultimate goal of L2 learning should be to engender in language students the willingness to look for communication opportunities and the willingness to communicate in them (McIntyre, Clement, Dornyei, & Noels, 1998). Willingness to communicate (WTC) is defined as the extent to which learners are prepared to initiate communication when they have a choice. It constitutes a factor believed to lead to individual differences in language learning (Maftoon & Amiri, 2012). Based on such an argument, they further proposed that to make willingness to communicate there should be an appropriate objective for second language education (Gol, Zand-Moghadam, & Karrabi, 2014).

MacIntyre (1994) developed a model to predict willingness to communicate in the first language. Based on this model, higher levels of willingness to communicate are caused by a combination of greater perceived communicative competence and a relative lack of communication apprehension. Introversion contributes to both communication apprehension and the perception of communicative competence, and self-esteem is in relation to communication apprehension. Finally, drawing upon Burgoon's (1976) findings, this model suggests that societal pressures (in the feelings of alienation and anomie) play a part in generating an unwillingness to communicate. MacIntyre (1994) recommended an exploring the interaction between personality and specific situational characteristics in their influence on willingness to communicate. MacIntyre et al. (1998) proposed a theoretical model with six layers consisting of a number of personalities, affective and situational constructs which then fall into two groups: stable, lasting factors (layers IV, V and VI), and situational, contextualized, and therefore changeable factors (layers I, II and III) (ibid. 546). (see Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Heuristic model of variables influencing WTC

Burgoon (1976) proposed the first construct on this field which is called “Unwillingness to Communicate” and defined it as “enduring and chronic tendency to avoid or devalue oral communication.” She reported that variables like anomie and alienation, introversion, self-esteem, and communication apprehension affect a person’s willingness for communication in different communication contexts. Literature on WTC is not short on original studies which have contributed to a better depiction of the relationship between WTC and other components of second language learning. Hashimoto (2002), for example, conducted a study to find out how WTC of Japanese learners of English as a second language and their motivation to use English were related. The findings revealed that motivation and WTC together could predict the frequency of communication in classroom contexts.

In another study, Clément et. al. (2003) aimed at investigating WTC and social context models together to probe the role of individuals and social factors in triggering the use of L2 in a group of Anglophone and Francophone students in Canada in comparison with Anglophone students who were learning French as their second language the Francophone learners of English as a second language who constituted the language minority in Canada were more willing to communicate in L2, and they were found to be more self-confident in classroom communication. Also, Yuki Hashimoto (2002) from university of Hawaii found motivation and willingness to communicate as predictors of reported L2 use in The Japanese context. In addition, some Iranian reserachers from different universities did studies on the issue. Valadi, Rezaee and Kogani (2016) investigated the relation between language learner's willingness to communicate and their oral language proficiencies with regard to gender differences. Alemi, tajeddin and Mesbah (2013) explored willingness to communicate in English as a foreign language.

A plethora of research has been done to clarify the role of social class on education. Some of them focused on EFL learning and the influence of social class and learners' economic level on different aspects of EFL learning. e.g. oral proficiency, students English language performance, EFL learner's language proficiency and so on (Valadi, Rezaee & Kogani, 2015). Social class is defined from different points of view. According to Moffit (2016) social class includes income, wealth, power, occupation, education, race and ethnicity and categorizes social class as: 1-the lower class 2-the working class 4-the middle class 5-the upper class. According to American Psychological Association (APA), socioeconomic status is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group, and it is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. Social influence is considered to have a significant impact on academic success (Schunk, 1999; Riese, Samara, & Lillejord, 2012). If learners are more able to maintain their social relationships with others in school, they are likely to perform better.

In the realm of second or foreign language (L2/FL) learning, there has been great interest among researchers and educators in how learners interact with one another for knowledge co-construction or the negotiation of meaning in traditional face-to-face settings in order to enhance linguistic knowledge in the target language (e.g., Foster & Ohta, 2005; Dobao, 2014). Salameh (2012) investigated the impact of social and economic factors on students’ English language performance in EFL classrooms in Dubai public secondary schools. The findings revealed that social factors are like behavioral factors which have a real dominance on one’s life. Family and school are considered as the two main social environments in which a child grows, so there is a harmony between the learner and his/her environment.

Language practitioners should recognize the fact that willingness to speak is an important factor that deserves more attention and consideration. Without creating willingness to speak among learners, the efforts teachers make in producing autonomous learners would be all in vain. As MacIntyre et al. (1998) stated, an important goal of language education should be creating willingness to communicate, and that any educational program fails to produce students who are willing to use the language is simply a failed program. As such, identifying the possible ways through which learners' degree of willingness to communicate can be enhanced seems essential. If the goal of modern language pedagogy is to train language learners to be able to use language for effective communication, the factors that may enhance or reduce such willingness to speak need to be identified. Language professionals are thus recommended to identify such factors and take measures to obliterate those that hinder willingness to speak and develop those that boost such willingness. To our knowledge, only scant attention has been paid to the effect of social class on the learners' willingness to communicate and their tendency to continue their study and to get higher degree of proficiency. Therefore, this research investigates the relationship between social class on Iranian EFL learners' willingness to communicate and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. To achieve the goal of the study the following research questions have been proposed:

1. Is there any significant difference between Iranian EFL learners' WTC and their social class level?
2. Is there any significant difference between Iranian EFL learners' tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency and social class level?
3. Is there any significant relationship between EFL learner's willingness to communicate and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency?

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. DESIGN

This study fell under the classification of one shot design as it strived to explore the possible correlations among social class and willingness to communicate and also the tendency to improve proficiency. In fact, in all research questions of this study, the main purpose was to find correlation between the variables. More specifically, the study applied a descriptive research design in the sense that there was no manipulation of the variables in the research context. Due to availability and manageability of the participants, they were chosen based on convenience sampling.

2.2. PARTICIPANTS

Participants of the study were selected randomly from Iran Language Institute, Kermanshah, Iran. Given the non-coeducational policy of the institute, we had two gender-based groups: female group (n=29) and male group (n=26). Based on the institute's placement criteria, they were high intermediate students and the age ranged from 12 to 18 years old. All the four skills, especially speaking, were worked on and emphasized in the institutes. The participants were trained by the same teaching method and they studied the same textbooks under the instruction of proficient English language teachers. The institute followed standard teaching practices and all language teachers were required to follow the classroom procedures of the institute.

2.3. INSTRUMENTS

In the present study, the researcher applied two questionnaires which were distributed simultaneously.

2.3.1. WTC QUESTIONNAIRE

To measure learners' WTC levels, a modified version of the Likert-scale questionnaire, developed by MacIntyre, Clement, and Conrod (2001), was distributed among the participants. The questionnaire includes 25 items related to the factors contributing to WTC in learning a second language. The scales ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). For the purpose of gathering required data regarding the effect of social class on the learners' tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency a question was added to the WTC questionnaire accordingly (question number 26). The learners were asked to select their answers to the items across the continuum. The reliability of the WTC questionnaire, tested by Cronbach's alpha, was 0.87.

2.3.2. SOCIO-ECONOMIC QUESTIONNAIRE

To determine students' social class, a revised version of Wolftang's (1999) questionnaire was administered. Different views on factors to be included in determining one's social class were considered and to make it suitable for the study, several open-ended questions were added. After revision, it was piloted, re-examined and finally administered as an 11-item social class questionnaire (a copy of which is provided in Appendix B), comprising 10 multi-choice questions with a variable number of choices and one open-ended question (each choice is indicative of a different level of social class). Cronbach's alpha for the reliability of the social class questionnaire in this study turned out to be .75. For the purpose of gathering required data and getting enough information about the effect of social class on the learners' tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency a question was added to the WTC questioner accordingly (question number 26).

2.4. PROCEDURES

In order to measure the learners' WTC levels, a modified version of the Likert-type questionnaire developed by MacIntyre (2001), Baghai and Dourakhshan (2011) was distributed among the participants. Furthermore, a few context-bound adaptation were made to the items. The questionnaire (see the appendix A) included 26 items, 25 of which were relevant to the factors contributing to WTC in learning a second language and one question (question number 26) was related to the second question which considered the effect of social class on the learners' willingness to achieve higher degree of proficiency. The questionnaire items were explained and clarified by the researcher to the participants to avoid any possible misunderstandings and to increase the validity of responses. The questionnaire followed a Likert type scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The learners were asked to indicate their responses to the items across the continuum. Reliability checks on the questionnaire based on a pilot study yielded an alpha estimate of 0.89.

Along with the questionnaire, short interviews were held with some of the participants randomly to approve their responses. To prevent the participants from running through the questionnaire items they were given enough time. Along with the WTC questionnaire the social class questionnaire was distributed among participants. The social class questionnaire contained 11 questions which was not a Likert one but a combination of some types of questions such as multiple choice, yes/no question, free answer question and question with more than one answer. The merit of the questionnaire was that the learner was not limited to one type of questions. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire was checked by Islami and his colleagues in 2014 and yielded an alpha estimate of 0.83.

2.5. DATA ANALYSES

One-way ANOVA and Post Hoc Test (Scheffe Test) was used to determine the difference between participants' willingness to communicate with regard to their social class level and also their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. The Pearson correlation coefficient clarified the amount of correlation between learners' willingness to communicate and their tendency to achieve a higher degree of proficiency.

3. RESULTS

This research was going to answer three questions. First, whether there is any significant relationship between the EFL learner's social class and their willingness to communicate, second whether there is any relationship between the EFL learners' social class and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. Also the relationship between the learners' willingness to communicate and their tendency to get higher degree of proficiency was investigated.

First of all, descriptive statistics, the Means and Standard Deviation of WTC questionnaire was measured, see Table 1.

Table 1- Descriptive Statistics of WTC and Social class

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
WTC	55	45	117	84.51	16.419
SO	55	10	37	25.25	6.456
Valid N (listwise)	55				

As the table shows minimum mark for WTC questionnaire was 45 and maximum 117 and standard deviation is 16.419. And also total mean for WTC is 84.51. Also, the minimum mark for social class was 10 and maximum 37 and standard deviation was 6.456.

3.1. ADDRESSING THE FIRST RESEARCH QUESTION

To find out the relationship between three groups of WTC which was classified according to their social class level, a one-way ANOVA was used. Table 2 determines this relationship.

Table 2- Relationship between social class and WTC

WTC					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5948.013	2	2974.006	17.962	.000
Within Groups	8609.733	52	165.572		
Total	14557.745	54			

Table 2 shows that the mean WTC of the three social groups are significantly different ($F=17.962$, $Sig=.000$). Then, In order to find the amount of relationship among 3 groups of participants regarding their willing to communicate, a multiple comparison test was required, see Table 3.

Table 3- Proportions of social class and WTC

(I) SOCIAL	(J) SOCIAL	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	11.813*	4.033	.019	1.65	21.97
	3	30.199*	5.040	.000	17.50	42.90
2	1	-11.813*	4.033	.019	-21.97	-1.65
	3	18.386*	4.579	.001	6.85	29.92
3	1	-30.199*	5.040	.000	-42.90	-17.50
	2	-18.386*	4.579	.001	-29.92	-6.85

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

As the table shows three groups are different from each other that means those participants which belong to the first social class group (group1) are significantly different from those in group 2 on their willingness to communicate which means group 1 social class are more motivated to communicate the language he/she is learning. The comparison among other groups also shows this justification. . Group 1 and 3 are also strongly different ($Sig=.000$) which means that those participants that belong to group3 are less motivated to communicate the language he/she is learning. Mean Differences between group2 and 3 is also significant ($Sig=.001$). Learners from second social class are more willing to communicate than those who belong to group 3. Thus, there's positive relationship between Iranian EFL learners' social class level and their willingness to communicate (WTC).

3.2. ADDRESSING THE SECOND RESEARCH QUESTION

To seek the answer of the second question a one-way ANOVA was run. The same as the first question, the learners' tendency for higher proficiency was classified according to their social class levels, see Table 4.

Table 4-Relationship between social class and higher degree of proficiency

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	38.012	2	19.006	33.692	.000
Within Groups	29.334	52	.564		
Total	67.345	54			

Table 4 shows the means between 3 groups is significantly different. We the ran a Post Hoc test to find more about the amount of differences.

Table 5- Proportions of social class and higher degree of proficiency

(I) SOCIAL	(J) SOCIAL	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	.973*	.235	.001	.38	1.57
	3	2.415*	.294	.000	1.67	3.16
2	1	-.973*	.235	.001	-1.57	-.38
	3	1.442*	.267	.000	.77	2.12
3	1	-2.415*	.294	.000	-3.16	-1.67
	2	-1.442*	.267	.000	-2.12	-.77

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Note: 1=high social class 2=middle social class 3=low social class Hpro=higher degree of proficiency
Table 5 clearly shows the amount of mean differences between 3 social class participants regarding their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. Group 1 and 2 are significantly different ($P < 0.05$) and the mean difference is .973. Groups 1 and 3 are also different ($P < 0.05$) and the mean difference is 2.415 which shows great differences between two groups and also the differences between groups 2 and 3 is significant. ($P < 0.05$) and mean difference is 1.442. So there is a positive relationship between the Iranian EFL learners' social class and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency.

3.3. ADDRESSING THE THIRD RESEARCH QUESTION

The relationship between willingness to communicate levels of the EFL learners (as measured by the WTC questionnaire) and their tendency for higher degree of proficiency of the participants (as measured by the questionnaire) was investigated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. Preliminary analysis revealed that the assumptions of normality, linearity and homoscedasticity were not violated. There was a strong correlation between the two variables, ($r = .416$, $n = 55$, $p < .005$) with high levels of perceived control associated with lower levels perceived stress, showing that there was a positive correlation between the participants' willingness to communicate and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. According this explanation and what we see in Table 6, the answer for the third question is obvious; There is a significant relationship between the Iranian EFL learners' willingness to communicate (WTC) and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency.

Table 6- Relationship between WTC and higher proficiency

		HPro	WTC
HPro	Pearson Correlation	1	.416**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	55	55
WTC	Pearson Correlation	.416**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	55	55

4. DISCUSSION

The current study aimed at investigating the relationship between willingness to communicate and social class level of Iranian EFL learners and their tendency to get higher degree of proficiency. First, the findings of the study as derived from the statistical analysis in the preceding section confirms that the willingness to communicate of the learners which was classified into 3 groups according to their social class level was significantly different. The learners belonging to higher social class are more willing to communicate than low social class learners. The finding of this research is in line with Salameh (2012) which indicates that the parents' education, parents' financial status and parents' occupation have impact on Students' English performance and also the result of the present study is supported by latest research done by Amirabadi (2017) concluded that there is a significant relationship between social class factors, cultural factors , linguistic factors and English proficiency.

This study also indicated that there is positive relationship between the learners' social class level and their tendency to achieve higher degree of proficiency. Statistical analysis shows that low social class

learners have less tendency to continue their language learning and get higher degree of proficiency and of course high social class learners are more motivated to get higher proficiency. This result is supported by Curren et al., (2007) reported that individuals with lower socioeconomic backgrounds who graduate from college are far less likely to pursue an advanced degree than their peers from more affluent backgrounds.. For the third question, the result shows a positive relationship between two variables. So those learners who are more willing to communicate have more tendency to continue their language learning process. This result is also in line with Alemi and colleagues (2011) which concluded Iranian university students' willingness to communicate was directly related to their language proficiency.

The findings revealed that learners with a high level of willingness to communicate belonged to the higher level of social class. The obtained results were in line with Valadi, Rezaee, & Kogani, (2015) which identified WTC and oral language proficiency as two variables positively correlated. In another study, Baghaei and Dourakhshan (2012) found a moderate correlation between willingness to communicate and English proficiency among EFL learners which their conclusion supports the result of the present study.

According to the results of the analysis, there was not a significant difference between male and female students in terms of willingness to communicate. This result is in contrast to the findings of the study conducted by Ahmadian and Shirvani (2012) that showed that there was a significant difference between male and female with regard to their willingness to communicate in Iranian EFL context. As mentioned earlier, gender difference must be accompanied by a number of other sociopolitical factors if we want to get a clear picture of the role that gender can play

5. CONCLUSION

It has been empirically shown that willingness to communicate is one of the factors influencing language learner's propensity to communicate in an ESL and EFL context. Willingness to communicate can be both enduring and situational, meaning that numerous factors surrounding learners might affect their decisions to communicate their meanings through L2 language they are learning. However, not much research has been carried out in foreign contexts where English is most often used for academic purposes..

This study can be considered as one of the few studies which focused on demographic and educational aspects of the concept of willingness to communicate in a specific educational setting. Finally, as Riasati (2015) states:" If the goal of modern language pedagogy is to train language learners to be able to use language for effective communication, the factors that may enhance or reduce such willingness to speak need to identify. Language professionals thus recommend to identify such factors and take measures to obliterate those that hinder willingness to speak and develop those that boost such willingness." (p.221)

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Appendix A

The questionnaire to measure willingness to communicate

Dear student:

The following questions ask about your willingness to communicate in learning English language. Remember, there are no right or wrong answers. Just answer as accurately as possible. Use the below scale to answer the questions.

	Strongly disagree	disagree	No idea	agree	Strongly agree
1.learning English is really interesting for me					
2.I wish I could speak many foreign languages					
3.Studying English is important because I can understand the new world better.					
4.I would like to go abroad and learn more about foreign countries and cultures					
5.The more I learn English the more I want to study it.					
6.I desire to learn an L2 in order to take part in the social community of L2-users					
7.Speaking and communicating in English with others is not difficult.					
8.I keep up to date with English by working on it almost every day.					
9.I think learning English is not just grammar and vocabulary.					
10. I do not prefer an English class which is teacher-centered and students are silent.					
11. In order to improve my English , I am willing to talk in English with my classmates inside the class.					
12. In order to improve my English, I am interested in communicating with others outside the class.					
13. Learning English provides opportunities to introduce Iranian rich culture to foreign countries.					
14. I prefer to be silent in EFL classes because talking in English makes me anxious.					
15.When I am studying English, I ignore distractions and pay attention to my task.					
16. I am willing to ask and answer questions in English in the class.					
17.I would like to participate in class discussions to show my English competence.					
18. I am relaxed to give presentation in front of my classmates.					
19. I am willing to express my opinion and feeling in English in private and public occasions.					
20. I send message and email in English to my friends and teachers.					
21. When talking in English in class, I lose my confidence and concentration.					
22. I have a strong desire to know all aspects of the English language.					
23. I watch and listen to English music, films and the news					
24. If I encounter native and non-native English speakers, I hope an opportunity would arise and they would talk to me.					
25. If I encounter native and non-native English speakers, I would find an excuse and talk to them.					
26. I would like to achieve higher degree of proficiency.					